

ISSN : 2348-0114

मूल्य : ₹ 500

वर्ष : 2

अंक : 7

(मई 2015-जुलाई 2015)

www.chintanresearchjournal.com

मुख्य-संपादक
आचार्य शीलक राम

चिन्तन

(International Refereed)

कला, साहित्य, मानविकी, समाज-विज्ञान, वाणिज्य, प्रबंधन, विधि एवं
विज्ञान विषयों का अंतर्राष्ट्रीय मूल्यांकित त्रैमासिक रिसर्च जर्नल

(आचार्य अकादमी, भारत)

ISO : 9001:2008

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Role Of Sustainable Development Management To Solve The Environmental Problems

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Abstract

India is growing fast and sustainable development becomes increasingly more important: According to a United Nations report, India's population currently encompasses about 1.2 billion people and is expected to grow by another 300 million within the next couple of decades. With cities generating two-thirds of the country's economic output, an increasing number of Indians are leaving rural areas to seek employment in cities, relying on an efficient urban infrastructure. By 2030 it is predicted that 68 Indian cities will each have more than one million inhabitants, and six megacities, more than ten million each. The rapid growth of cities causes a large number of challenges specially challenges related to environment. The paper shows that environment is one of the basic public assets of a human system, and it must be therefore specially protected. According to our present knowledge, the sustainability is necessary for all human systems and it is necessary to invoke the sustainable development principles in all human system assets. Sustainable development is understood as a development that does not erode ecological, social or politic systems on which it depends, but it explicitly approves ecological limitation under the economic activity frame and it has full comprehension for support of human needs. The paper summarizes the conditions for sustainable development, strategies, tools, methods, and techniques to solve the environmental problems and the tasks of executive governance in the environmental segment.

Key-Words : Sustainable development, Environment, Population.

Introduction

Environment literally means surrounding and everything that affect an organism during its lifetime is collectively known as its environment. In another words "Environment is sum total of water, air and land interrelationships among themselves and also with the human being, other living organisms and property". It includes all the physical and biological surrounding and their interactions. Environmental studies provide an approach towards understanding the environment of our planet and the impact of human life upon the environment. Thus environment is actually global in nature, it is a multidisciplinary subject including physics, geology, geography, history, economics, physiology, biotechnology, remote sensing, geophysics, soil science and hydrology.

The concept of Sustainability has been enshrined in the Indian thought process since ancient times. It is a holistic concept which has been emerged from the changing relationship between Man and environment. They are mutually, thus in exclusive. Our Vedic literature is full of

the ideas of Sustainability. The ancient Scripture say so out of reverence for all, the material and the spiritual, the human and the animal, the spoken and the unspoken. For all Species including human beings, for all who can and for all those who cannot.

The environment itself is a system of systems that, from the viewpoint of human existence and development, is a part of the superior system of systems, the human system. From the given fact that it is evidently impossible to elevate the environment existence and return to original state under the interests connected with human existence and development, but, simultaneously, it is impossible to damage the environment irresponsibly, because it creates the medium necessary for human existence itself. Therefore, we have to introduce the compromises that respect human needs and environment into the practice, based on our knowledge and experience. Their impact and benefits are monitored in the way that allows carrying out the corrective measures if they seem to be necessary.

Based on recent cognition, sustainability (sustainable development), is not only related to the environment, but also to the entire human system and its basic assets i.e. purely public assets on which the human lives are dependent. Basic human system assets are human lives, health and security; environment; property and public welfare; infrastructures and technologies, in particular those that belong to the critical ones. The sustainability assessment in general sense is the formalized process for identification, prediction and assessment of potential impact of arbitrary inputs including the variants for society sustainable development (e.g. legal rules, ordinances, regulations, political intent, plan, program, and project). From the viewpoint of present cognition of human system and its assets, the mentioned assessment might be performed always at good governance of territory.

Conditions for sustainable development

From the system viewpoint, the sustainable system has attributes as productivity, adaptability and vulnerability, and therefore, sometimes it is not easy to find a suitable reference state or conditions:

- The reference point of sustainability is a demanded future state (scenarios, techniques and foresight).
- The reference points are, on the one hand, inputs and, on the other hand, outputs of system processes (ecological trace, product life times etc.).

Tools, methods and techniques for solutions to environmental problems

The humans did not come in the environment with intent to subvert the nature. The problems started at the time when humans tried to separate themselves from the nature, and they placed technology / engineering between themselves and the nature. Initially, it was not evident, the biosphere has kept its reserves and it contrived to equilibrate with a range of activities. However, the human activity has been progressively taking on the intensity and in some directions the biosphere has been globally affected.

The present worldwide problems are of a global character. Apart from the environment Contamination, other major global problems involve the questions of peace and war, the differences between developed and developing countries, providing the food for future population, energy demand, lack of water, soil, sources, as well as the questions of health care, culture and education. THEREFORE, it is necessary to introduce STRATEGIC, SYSTEM AND PROACTIVE MANAGEMENT based

on a realistic, systematic and proactive view of human system and its problems. The given view is necessary from the following reasons:

- Humans have been getting to a certain life standard that they do not repudiate; this standard is conditioned by interventions to nature.
- The environment is an adaptable system. During their development, the humans have accumulated much knowledge and experience, and therefore, they are supposed to know the ways to limit the interventions to a system, so that to ensure the system development in the direction supporting the mankind's development.
- For many humans, the environment today represents a stylish stalking horse which makes them take up the actions that have nothing in common with real environment (e.g. the reality that the soil is left unexploited does not prosper to environment).

Strategies for Sustainable Development Suggested by Haubrich 2007

There are several strategies which have been suggested to achieve Sustainable Development. Some of these are:-

1. Efficiency Strategy- This is possible through innovations in technical and organizational functions.
2. Consistency Strategy- This may be achieved through renewable resources.
3. Permanency Strategy- This aims at enhancing life span of products through technology.
4. Sufficiency Strategy- This lays emphasis on changing consumption pattern through new life Style.
5. Education and social commitment Strategy- The education and social commitment Strategy help by promoting awareness for social justice among the people.

There are one another Strategy known as environmental ethics Strategy may also be added.

6. Environmental Ethics Strategy- This relates to ethics contained in our ancient scriptures to conserve the eco-system. The way first Mantra of Isopnis had one of the foremost. India's books of ancient wisdom says, "Everything in this creation is owned and controlled by the Lord. One should, therefore accept those things necessary for himself, which are set aside for his quota and one should not accept other things, knowing well to whom they belong." This idea needs a kind of ethical revolution, a task which may be taken up by the young geographers to familiarise and popularize the concept and need of Sustainable Development.

For decision-making, a model of environment that is restricted to human medium has been used, because the aim of human strive is to ensure the human society development, i.e. by recent words said the such development trajectory of whole environment system that onward enables humankind development. Based on the present knowledge each quality management, including environmental management, must carry out the decision-making process with respect to the following goals:

- To prevent emergency situations and to localize emergency situations (the accidents can origin in the frame of both, individual components or even in the frame of the whole environment system),
- To ensure the healthy development of human society,
- to implement ecological programmes in the socio-economic sphere.

The management must monitor

- Impacts of anthropogenic activities into the environment that can be divided into:

• Pollution of environment component (may be either of the material character, manifested by concentrations of agents or of physical origin manifested by noise, heat, electromagnetic oscillation etc.,

- Biologic diversity, i.e. reduction of number of species, change of species composition etc.,
- Deterioration of health state of human population,
- Pressure of antropogenic sphere on environment that is divided to:
- Emissions of agents (or better wastes of human activities) into natural medium,
- Consumption of renewable sources.

Administration management and its tasks on environment sector

Since its origin, the basic function of state has been to ensure the protection and development of a given human society which is impossible without ensuring the safe space in that the human society has been living. The management of state includes generally the concepts of government, control and office hearing of the public affairs. It represents the conscious activity that is directed to the determination and control of course of topical processes for achievement of appointed goals. It puts individual activities in harmony and it fulfils general functions of the whole, i.e. the state / territory / object / organization etc. The governance is the form of activity of authorities, particularly executive ones that consists in organizing and practical implementation of tasks given by managing team / state management/ territory / object / organization in harmony with laws and the other legal rules.

According to the basic tools of state for management directed to sustainability are:

• Management (strategic, tactical, operational) based on qualified data, knowledge, professional assessments, qualified decision-making methods, land-use planning, correct sitting, designing, building, operation, maintenance, reparation and renovation of buildings, technologies and infrastructures,

- citizen's education, schooling and training,
- specific education of technical and management workers,
- technical, health, ecological, cyber and other standards, norms and rules including the best practice procedures, i.e. tools for control/regulation of processes that may or might lead to

disaster occurrence or to the increase of its impact,

- inspections and audits,
- executive security forces for qualified response to emergency and critical situations,
- systems for critical situations defeating,
- security (land-use and spatial), emergency, continuity, crisis and contingency planning,
- specific system for defeating the critical situations - safety, emergency, continuity and crisis management.

The analysis of the development of environment and the development of political, social and economic situation worldwide shows that it is necessary to solve the cases and actions that by their intensity induce the critical situations leading to relevant crises of the type denoted as a humanitarian catastrophe or social crisis.

Therefore, from the viewpoint of human security, human system development, conservation of quality environment, existence, stability and development of state must comprise a safety concept connected with the concepts of development codified and implemented by safety

management. On the basic (usual) level of management, the target is security and sustainable development, thus connecting emergency and crisis management.

The goal of human society management is to ensure the protection of: human lives, health and security; property, welfare; environment; infrastructures and technologies, which are inevitable for human survival, i.e. the mobilization and co-ordination of utilization of national sources (energy, labor force, production capability, food and agriculture, resources, telecommunications etc.), the co-ordination of such activities as they are notification system, rescue system and medical services that reduce impacts of natural or other disasters and ensures the continuity of activity of public administration, the adherence of legislation and also generate the conditions for start of development

The land and regional development is manifested by the construction of industrial regions coming closer and closer to the residential zones. Possibility of harm thus increases, and society (community) is not willing to accept all risks. This is the reason for the necessity of risk management and consecutively risk engineering that includes risk assessment, risk reduction and harm explanation. In short, the risk engineering is connected with technical systems (only in advanced forms, the human factor influence on complex process safety is considered) and in the broader sense, it is possible to generalize it to renewal of landscape with utilization of engineering approaches. Therefore, the risk engineering plays such an important role. Its target, on the one hand, is the optimum protection of humans, property and environment, and, on the other hand, the optimum renewal of damaged landscape with utilization of engineering procedures and findings. Both concepts require structured a system approach and qualified utilization of planning the scenarios for decision-making support.

The territory management understood as strategic and proactive territory safety management differs from normal environment management in the following items:

- It is directed to the long-term sustainability.
- The aim is the system integrity (including the so called ecological integrity) because ecosystem services/utilities (i.e. utilities that environment offers to humans) promotes live supporting functions.
- It considers the human as an element of system and it integrates human activity with environment protection.
- It sentient reacts to human needs in the system contexts. It includes quality environment management.

Conclusion

From the viewpoint of society needs, it is necessary to ensure the further development of economy on the one hand, and, on the other hand, to reduce the environment contamination and to ensure the environment protection. The artistic creation is the high degree of proficiency. The complex problems of the human/nature relation are based on certain philosophical foundations in each historical era.

The present period can be characterized as the era in which the humans incessantly start turning the higher merry-go-round of substances and energies in order to satisfy their needs, with reality that the bulk of these substances is growing much faster than the human needs.

On one side it displays deficiencies of resources and energy (resource stocks have been stretched) and on the other side it wastes with resources and with energy.

Sustainability considers the nature and human from the viewpoint of optimum development of the whole biosphere. The ecological behaviour should not be reduced to the riotous discussions around the nuclear power plants and water structures or industrial complexes. We must plan and build big structures. At the same time, we must consider the impacts of these constructions on the environment and human health.

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